

MARKETING PROBLEMS AND THEIR IMPACT ON ORCHID FARMERS OF KASHMIR (J&K)

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Abstract: *Marketing plays a vital role to determine the need and demand of different commodities produced by farmers. It develops a link between sellers and buyers of a commodity at a mutually accepted price. It plays an important role in horticultural process by enabling horticulturalists to sell their produce and get associated privileges in shape of cash and kind. Every crop production in general and cash crops and fruits in particular are weighted and valued on the basis of their market value. Marketing of horticultural product is directly associated with availability of markets besides social and economic status of the cultivators. Marketing of the produce may be carried forward either by directly or indirectly. It is affected by various factors ranging from availability of cold stores and local markets to transportation and commission agent charges besides political environment of that particular region. The reasons which propagate these problems are illiteracy and unawareness of horticulturalists, faulty institutional loan systems and lack of industries and factories for processing of the produce. The present study highlights marketing problems and their impact on orchid farmers in Kashmir.*

Key Words: Cold Stores, Commission Agents, Crop Value, Horticulturalists, Orchid Farmers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is regarded very important pursuit carried forward by farmers in rural areas to sustain their living. It has taken shape of primary occupation of almost all village dwellers and is regarded to shape up their way of living by modifying their social and economic status. The future of Indian agricultural is challenging (Thakur and Kumar; 2009) because of multidimensional problems which range from storage and

packaging to maintenance besides marketing and inefficient rural transport system (United Nations; 2003). The carried forward activities by farmers in villages were initially subsistence based but later as of change in need and demand of market value it changed to profit base. These shifts lead towards change in cultivation and cropping patterns which resulted into land-use change. The land use change isn't only confined to few crops changed or taken but is also associated with some holistic shifts. One amongst such shifts is from agriculture towards horticulture. Horticulture is preferred over agriculture because of its increasing demand in markets and associated profits. Horticulture is carried forward generally on small chunks of land for mixed crops rather than large ones for single crops. It includes intensive cultivation of plants for human use based on science and technology besides other related aspects and is practiced in a garden from individual level up to the level of Multinational Corporation (MNCs). Horticulture incorporates plants for food and other related services like conservation of plants and landscape restoration etc. This range of food, medicinal, environmental, and social products and services are all fundamental to developing and maintaining human health and well-being (Doyle, et al; 2012). Horticulture is getting negatively affected by infrastructure as well as market limitations. The various problems are being confronted by horticulturalists while practicing horticulture. Markets play a very decisive role in promotion and distribution of any produce. The problems affect not only quality and quantity of produce but also affect its marketing to a large extent. Therefore, these problems need to be addressed at their earliest as their uncontrollable increase may have adverse effect on horticultural produce which is regarded as backbone of Indian economy.

India ranks second in the world in the production of fruits and vegetables after China as of diverse agro-climatic regions. Horticultural practices need feasible climatic condition due to which it is not practiced thought the country but in some regions which are most favorable for such productions. Apart from bringing in revenue from exports, horticulture plays a significant role in improving the livelihood of the rural population. Apple is regarded as a major fruit crop of temperate regions of the whole world. In India, it has become an important cash crop in few states of India such as Himachal Pradesh and Jammu and Kashmir. It has helped greatly in improving socio-economic status of the farmers of these areas where land has not remained otherwise ideal for traditional farming besides supplying healthy and nutritious food to people.

The study area (Jammu and Kashmir State) is mountainous and is located in the North of the Indian sub-continent. The state is divided into three major divisions- Jammu, Kashmir and Ladakh, which differ in terms of culture, geography and climate. The total area of Jammu and Kashmir State is 2416 thousand hectares among which only 31 per cent is available for cultivation and rest of the land is under forests (Wani ; 2009). With increasing industrialization and urbanization, various shifts have taken place in marketing process of the produce. Just like other states of India, Jammu and Kashmir has also witnessed the change in land use patterns due to which marketing has also under gone change. More than 65 per cent of the population of the valley depend upon agriculture and allied agro vocations. It is also revealed with regard to marketing that price risk is faced by cultivators as there is no guarantee of increasing trend in market price besides no support is being provided by the government in home markets (Malik ; 2013). The research paper highlights the problems faced by horticulturalists in district Shopian of Kashmir (Jammu and Kashmir).

2. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in district Shopian of Jammu and Kashmir because most of the population (rural and urban) is associated with horticulture. (Fig.1). The population and area/square kilometer of district Shopian is 265,960; 312. The proportion of rural and urban population in district Shopian is 94.38 percent, 5.62 percent (census 2011). District Shopian is historically very much important as it is situated on ancient imperial route commonly known as Mughal road which connects Lahore and Srinagar initially and now connects Shopian with Poonch, Rajouri and Jammu. It is Situated 2146 mts above the sea level and is 51Kms away from Srinagar. District Shopian has two Assembly constituencies, one Tehsil and 2 CD Blocks besides 43 Patwar Halqas and 231 inhabited villages. The District is entitled as apple bowl of the state and is very famous for Horticultural production. District has tremendous scope for fruit industry, the proper execution of which may boost the economy of the district in particular and state in general very rapidly. District has an area of 30,741.6 hectares (312 sq km) and is Hilly Terrain. District consists of 231 villages, distributed in 2 blocks -block Shopian (181 villages) and block Keller (80 villages). 10 villages were randomly selected through fish bowl technique from both the blocks proportionately – 6 villages from block Shopian and 4 villages from block Keller. Among these selected 10 villages 320 respondents were

selected through proportionate sampling. From each selected village respondents are selected from marginal, small, medium and large farmer categories randomly. Interview schedule was prepared to gather the information. The data so collected was analyzed, coded and tabulated in the light of prefixed objectives of the study and conclusions are drawn.

3. MARKETING

Marketing plays a very vital role for any sort of production since its inception, processing and production. Market is such an institution or business zone which develops link between those who seek to sale commodity with those who wish to purchase it at an exchange value of mutually accepted price (Darity; 2008). Markets are referred to such business zones where exchange of goods and services take place. Marketing plays an important role in horticultural practice as it helps horticulturalists to sell their produce and to get associated privileges in shape of both cash and kind. Every production in general and cash crops in particular are weighted and valued on the basis of their market value. The change in need and demand of particular commodity is directly associated with demands posed by markets. The study area is very famous for apple industry and majority of the population depends on it directly or indirectly. Farmers produce various fruits among which apples are being regarded as most preferred ones. It has become primary occupation of majority of farmers, so its proper and sound marketing is a great apprehension for social and economic upliftment of their status. The marketing in the study area is mainly carried out by two ways- directly from producer to commission agents in market (Producer → Commission Agents → Markets) and secondly from producer to local artiya and then to commission agents in markets (Producer → Money Lender cum-Commission agent → Market) (Fig.1.1).

Fig. 1.1: Marketing pattern of Orchid Farmers

4. SALE OF PRODUCT

The data with regard to sale of product by the respondents reveals that majority of the respondents (59.69 per cent) sell their product through money lender cum-commission agents (whom they have taken advance money) who later sells it to commission agents in mandi, whereas, the proportion of respondents who sell their product directly through commission in markets is 40 per cent (Table 1.1). The farmer category wise analysis reveals that majority of marginal and small farmers (90 per cent and 62 per cent respectively) sell their product to artiya where as a small proportion among them (10 per cent and 38 per cent respectively) sell their product directly in markets to commission agents. The analysis further reveals that majority of medium and large farmers (61 per cent and 93 per cent respectively) sell their product directly in markets to commission agents, whereas, a small proportion among them (39 per cent and 7 per cent respectively) sell their product through money lender cum-commission agents. So,

it may be said that marginal and small farmers sell their product through money lender cum commission agents as they may be indebted to them because of advance money and medium and large farmers sell directly to commission agents in mandi, which may be because of their non-indebtedness towards money lenders as of their sound economic status.

Sale	Number of the Respondent (Farmer category)				Total
	Marginal	Small	Medium	Large	
Through Commission Agents	9 (10.11)	42 (37.84)	64 (60.95)	14 (93.33)	129 (40.31)
Through Money Lender Cum - Commission Agents	80 (89.89)	69 (62.16)	41 (39.05)	1 (6.67)	191 (59.69)
Total	89 (27.81)	111 (34.69)	105 (32.81)	15 (4.69)	320 (100)

Table 1.1: Sale of product

5. PREFERRED MARKETING FOR PRODUCT

It is obvious that majority of the respondents sell their product through commission agents, however, there is difference in actual and preferred type of marketing. The data with regard to preferred marketing reveals that majority of the respondents (82.81 per cent) prefer to sell their product directly in markets through commission agents, whereas the money lender cum-commission agents mediated marketing is preferred by least proportion of the respondents i.e., 17 per cent (Table 1.2). The class wise analysis of respondents shows that almost an equal proportion of small and medium farmers (35 per cent each) prefer to sell their product directly in markets followed by marginal and larger farmers which constitute 23.02 per cent and 5.66 per cent respectively. The farmer category wise analysis of data with regard to reasons behind direct market preference reflects that most of the marginal farmers (40.45 per cent) hold the view that direct selling in markets provides them more profit, it is followed by 22 per cent of them who are of view that direct type of marketing protects them from paying any commission to local artiya. This type of marketing gives them freedom to bargain on rates of their product is reported by 5.46 per cent of the marginal farmers. Most of the small farmers (32 per cent) are of view that it helps them to earn more profit; it is followed by 25 per cent of them who reflect that it helps them to withhold produce for some time especially

during low market rates. The proportion of small farmers who are of view that direct marketing protects them from paying commission to money lenders is slightly higher (14 per cent) than those farmers who regard it to provide recognition in markets (12 per cent). A small proportion of the small farmers (3 per cent) reveal that it provides freedom to bargain on rates of their product. Among medium farmers majority i.e., 69 per cent are of view that direct marketing provides more profit to them, it is followed by 9.52 per cent of them who are of view that it provides them recognition in markets. An equal proportion of medium farmers (4 per cent each) are of view that it gives freedom to bargain of rates and protects them from paying any commission to local artiya besides it allows them to withhold produce during low market rates. Among large farmers majority (53 per cent) is of view that this marketing helps them to attain more profit whereas, 47 per cent among them reveal that it provides them recognition in markets.

The study with regard to preference for local artiya based marketing reveals that 50 per cent of the marginal farmers show preference for money lender cum-commission agent based marketing; it is followed by the small and medium farmers which comprise of 30 per cent and 20 per cent respectively. The farmer category wise analysis with regard to reasons reveal that 26 per cent of the marginal farmers uphold the low economic status as the reason for this type of marketing preference, it is followed by 3 per cent among them who regard hectic institutional loan procedure as the reason behind preference. The proportion of the marginal farmers who reflect that this type of marketing helps to avail money any time from artiya constitute of 2 per cent. Among the small farmers 11 per cent are of view that hectic procedure for institutional loan is the reason behind this preference, it is followed by 4 per cent of them who claim low economic status to be reason for preference. Some of the small farmers i.e., 2 per cent view that this marketing provides them freedom to get money anytime due to which they are not bound to wait till sale of their product. An equal proportion of the medium farmers (4 per cent each) reveals that artiya marketing helps them to get money anytime from them whenever need arises and hectic institutional loan procedure also pushes them for this marketing practice. So, it may be said that all of the large farmers followed by most of the small and medium farmers besides marginal farmers prefer to sell their product directly in markets to commission agents. Most of marginal, small, medium and large farmers hold that direct market sale of product provides them more profit. Artiya marketing is preferred majority of marginal

farmers followed by small and medium farmers; however, no large farmer shows preference for artiya mediated marketing. The most of marginal farmers regard low economic status as the reason for this type of marketing whereas; most of small and medium farmers regard hectic procedure for loan as the reason behind artiya marketing preference.

Preference	Reasons		Number of the Respondents (Farmer Category)				Total
			Marginal	Small	Medium	Large	
Through Commission agents	1	Need not to pay any commission or interest to local artiya	20 (22.47)	15 (13.51)	4 (3.81)	--	39 (12.20)
	2	Gives more profit	36 (40.45)	36 (32.43)	72 (68.57)	8 (53.33)	152 (47.50)
	3	Free to bargain of rates	5 (5.62)	3 (2.70)	4 (3.81)	--	12 (3.81)
	4	May withhold produce for some time	--	28 (25.23)	4 (3.81)	--	32 (10.00)
	5	Gives use recognition in markets	--	13 (11.71)	10 (9.52)	7 (46.67)	30 (9.40)
	Sub-total			61 (23.02)	95 (35.85)	94 (35.47)	15 (5.66)
Through Money lender cum-commission agents	1	May get money any time from them	2 (2.25)	--	4 (3.81)	--	6 (1.90)
	2	Need not to wait for money till product will be sold	--	2 (1.80)	--	--	2 (0.61)
	3	As of low economic status or background	23 (25.84)	4 (3.60)	--	--	27 (8.43)
	4	Hectic procedure of institutional loan	3 (3.37)	12 (10.81)	5 (4.76)	--	20 (6.25)
	Sub-total			28 (50.01)	16 (29.09)	11 (20.00)	
Total			89 (27.81)	111 (34.69)	105 (32.28)	15 (4.69)	320 100

Table 1.2: Preferred Marketing and Reasons

6. PROBLEMS FACED IN MARKETING

Markets simply refer to such an institution where exchange of goods and services take place. Marketing of the produce is very crucial and mandatory process as it transfers production into cash. A sound and hassle-free marketing of the product enhances its value. The analysis of data reflects that there is difference in actual and preferred marketing of the product by the respondents. It is obvious that for the sale of any product especially apple, better markets and buyers (commission agents and exporters) besides experience of seller plays a very vital role. Lack of these precautionary measures may lead towards marketing failures. The data with regard to problems faced by the respondents in marketing reveals that majority of the respondents (92.81 per cent) face problems in marketing process of their product, whereas, least number of the respondents (7.19 per cent) uphold an against view (Table 1.3). The land holding class wise analysis reveals that all of marginal and small farmer respondents face problems in marketing process of their product. Among medium farmers majority of the respondents 87 per cent face problems in marketing of their product, whereas 13 per cent among them are not facing any related problem. The majority of large farmers which comprise of 60 per cent are of view of not facing any problem in marketing process whereas, least proportion of them i.e., 40 per cent face problems in their marketing process. So, it may be said that marginal, small and medium farmers face marketing problems whereas, majority of large farmers do not face any problem in marketing process.

Problems faced	Number of the Respondents (Farmer category)				Total
	Marginal	Small	Medium	Large	
Yes	89 (100)	111 (100)	91 (86.67)	6 (40.00)	297 (92.81)
No	--	--	14 (13.33)	9 (60.00)	23 (7.19)
Total	89 (27.81)	111 (34.69)	105 (32.28)	15 (4.69)	320 (100)

Table 1.3: Problems faced in marketing

7. TYPES OF PROBLEMS FACED

The data with regard to different types of problems faced by respondents reveals that majority of the respondents (23.20 per cent) face less rates of their product in local markets (mandi) as of improper markets (Table 1.4). It is followed by (21.90 per cent) of the respondents who reflect high transportation rates as a problem faced in marketing process due to which they can't send their product to far away markets, from where they may fetch good rates. However, the problem of having no direct contact with exporters or commission agents as of which they fail to bargain for higher rates of their product is reflected by 19.20 per cent respondents. It is followed by 14.10 per cent of respondents who claim the issue of lack of fruit markets (mandi) in their area due to which they are bound to sell their product in only those one or few existing fruit trade centers (mandi) which are available to them in their areas. The proportion of 12 per cent of respondents regards lack of cold stores to uphold their product as a problem. The 6.40 per cent of the respondents claim to face the problem of unawareness about proper marketing patterns and processes. However, least number of the respondents i.e., 3.40 per cent claims the problem of high commission being charged by artiya. So, from the analysis it may be deduced that various problems are being faced by the horticulturalists which range from less rates being fetched by produce in markets to high transportation rates and lack of direct contact with exporters besides lack of fruit trade centers (mandi), less availability of cold stores and high commissions charged by artiya.

The landholding class wise analysis reveals that majority of the majority of marginal 28 per cent face the problem of less rates of their product in local markets. It is followed by 26 per cent among them who face the problem of high transportation rates for carrying their product to their respective markets. The problem of lack of fruit trade centers in their area and lack of direct contact with exporters is reported by 18 per cent and 13 per cent of marginal farmers respectively. The proportion of marginal farmers face the problem of cold stores to withhold their product is slightly higher (8 per cent) than least proportion (7 per cent) among them who highlight to face the problem of high commission charged by artiya. Among small farmers, majority of the respondents

i.e., 33 per cent face the problem of lack of direct contact with exporters and is followed by 26 per cent of respondents among them who regard high transportation rates for carrying product as problem. The problem of low rates fetched by product and lack of local fruit markets is reported by 21 per cent and 9 per cent of small farmers respectively. The proportion of 5 per cent of small farmers face problem of cold stores whereas, least number (2 per cent) among them face the problem of unawareness about proper marketing. Majority of the medium farmers (24 per cent) face the problem of cold stores to retain their product during low market rates. It is followed by 23 per cent and 18 per cent of medium farmers who regard less rates fetched by their produce in local markets and unawareness about proper marketing respectively. An equal proportion of the respondents (14 and 13 per cent) among medium farmers uphold high transportation rates and lack of local fruit trading markets as the problems faced in marketing process. The least number of the medium farmers (7 per cent) reflect no direct contact with exporters as a problem faced in marketing process. Among large farmers, majority (67 per cent) face the problem of lack of fruit trading centers in their areas whereas, 33 per cent face the problem of lack of direct contact with exporters. So, it may be said that marginal famers mostly face the problem regarding rates and small farmers the problem of direct contact with exporters, whereas, medium farmers face the problem of cold storage and large farmers the lack of fruit trading center besides other problems

Problems faced	Number of the Respondents (Farmer category)				Total
	Marginal	Small	Medium	Large	
Lack of fruit trade centers (mandi) in area	16 (17.98)	10 (9.00)	12 (13.19)	4 (66.67)	42 (14.10)
Unawareness about proper marketing	--	2 (1.80)	17 (18.68)	--	19 (6.40)
Produce fetches less rates in local markets	25 (28.09)	23 (20.72)	21 (23.08)	--	69 (23.20)
No direct contact with exporters	12 (13.48)	37 (33.33)	6 (6.59)	2 (33.33)	57 (19.20)
Lack of cold stores to withhold product	7 (7.86)	6 (5.41)	22 (24.18)	--	35 (11.80)
High transportation rates	23 (25.84)	29 (26.13)	13 (14.28)	--	65 (21.90)
High commission charged by Artiya	6 (6.74)	4 (3.60)	--	--	10 (3.40)
Total	89 (29.97)	111 (37.37)	91 (30.64)	6 (2.02)	297 (100)

Table 1.4: Type of problems faced in marketing

8. REASONS BEHIND VARIOUS PROBLEMS

Every problem is associated with some or the other reasons which sow its seeds. The data analysis (Table 1.3) reveals that marketing of the fruit production is not free from problems as majority of the respondents claim to face problems. That data with regard to reasons behind the problems faced by the respondents in marketing of their produce reveals that majority of the respondents (27.38 per cent) hold the view that lack of industries and factories for the processing of the produce is the reason behind problems faced by them in marketing (Table 1.5). The proportion of respondents who regard illiteracy and unawareness of marketing as a reason behind the problems faced in marketing of their product comprise of 25 per cent. It is followed by 22.36 per cent of the respondents who reflect that faulty institutional loan system as problem faced during marketing of product. They further revealed that the institutional loan disbursement is very hectic and lengthy due to which marketing problems get break

out. The number of respondents who uphold lack of government check on commission agents and transportation rates as the reason behind the marketing problems constitute of 16 per cent. The tense and volatile political environment of the region is also claimed to be a reason behind the problems faced in marketing of produce by least proportion of the respondents i.e., 9 per cent. So, it may be concluded from above analysis that multiple reasons which are responsible behind marketing problems range from lack of factories and industries to negligible check of government on commission agents and tense political environment of the region besides faulty institutional loan system and illiteracy and unawareness.

The landholding class wise analysis highlights that large number of the respondents who viewed about reasons behind the problems faced are medium farmers (38 per cent), followed by small and marginal which comprise of 31 per cent and 27 per cent respectively. The proportion of large farmers is least (4 per cent). The study further reveals among marginal farmers an equal proportion of respondents (44 per cent each) regard illiteracy and unawareness and lack of industries and factories for processing of their produce as reasons responsible for marketing problems faced by them. The reason of faulty institutional loan systems and no government check on commission agents and transportation charges is viewed reason by 8 per cent and 3 per cent of marginal farmers respectively. The tense and volatile political environment is the reason behind various problems faced in marketing of product is reported by least number of marginal farmers (1.30 per cent). The equal proportion of small farmers (32 per cent each) reveals that lack of industries and factories and illiteracy and unawareness are the reasons put forth by them behind marketing problems faced by them. It is followed by 13 per cent of them who claim faulty institutional loan systems as the reasons behind the marketing processes. An equal proportion of them (11 per cent each) are of view that no government check on commission agents and transportation charges and tense and volatile political environment is the reason behind the various marketing problems faced by them. The majority of medium farmers 40 per cent view faulty institutional loan system as the reason responsible for marketing problems faced by them. It is followed by 30 per cent of them who regard no government check on commission agents and transportation charges as the reason responsible. An equal proportion of them (12 per cent each) are of view that lack of industries and factories besides tense and volatile environment is the reason responsible for marketing problems faced by them. The least proportion among them (5 per cent) views that illiteracy and

unawareness is the reason responsible behind problems faced in marketing by them. Among large farmers an equal proportion of the respondents (26 per cent each) reveal that illiteracy and unawareness and lack of industries and factories are the reasons responsible behind marketing problems. The faulty loan systems and volatile and tense political environment is reported as reason by an equal proportion of large farmers (17 per cent each). The least proportion of them (13 per cent) view no government check on commission agents and transportation rates as the reasons responsible for marketing problems faced by them. So, it may be concluded that illiteracy and unawareness is reported as reason by large number of marginal, small and large farmers, whereas for faulty institutional loan system is claimed as reason by large number of medium farmers beside other reasons.

Reasons	Number of the Respondents (Farmer Category)				Total
	Marginal	Small	Medium	Large	
Illiteracy and unawareness	68 (44.16)	57 (31.67)	12 (5.45)	6 (26.09)	143 (24.78)
Faulty institutional loan systems	12 (7.80)	24 (13.33)	89 (40.45)	4 (17.39)	129 (22.36)
Tense and volatile political environment	2 (1.30)	20 (11.11)	27 (12.27)	4 (17.39)	53 (9.18)
Lack of industries and factories for processing of produce	67 (43.50)	58 (32.22)	27 (12.27)	6 (26.09)	158 (27.38)
No govt. check on commission agents and transportation charges	5 (3.24)	21 (11.67)	65 (29.55)	3 (13.04)	94 (16.29)
Total	154 (26.69)	180 (31.20)	220 (38.12)	23 (4.00)	577 (100)

*Multiple response question; N=577

Table 1.5: Reasons behind the problems

9. IMPACT OF THE PROBLEMS

The problems which horticulturalists confront during the process of their horticultural practice may affect the various aspects of their life as mostly the horticulture is the primary source of income and survival. The data (Table 1.6) with regard to impact of the problems faced in the marketing of the produce reveals that majority of the respondents 36.30 per cent hold the view that such problems decreases their social and economic status as horticulture being the primary source of their earning and income which are deterrent factors of social and economic status of a person. It is followed by 26.22 per cent of the respondents who reflect that such problems negatively affect their standard of life as being directly associated with monetary sources of a person, however, the respondents who uphold that such problems affect the education and marriage of their children constitute 84 (20.58 per cent) of the respondents. It is followed by 9.60 per cent of the respondents who claim that such problems lead to polarization of classes as commission agents become richer and sellers or producers become poorer as of which the social and economic status gap between deepens, however, it is followed by least number of the respondents (7.30 per cent) who reflect that such problems raise obstruction in various ongoing family developmental plans as mostly these problems stagnate their income due to which they fail to continue their various ongoing developmental plans or programs. So, it is to be revealed that such problems have multidimensional impacts on the various aspects of the horticulturalists which range from decrease in social and economic status, negative affect on standard of life, effect on education and marriage of children to polarization of classes and becomes obstruction in various ongoing family developmental plans and programs.

Impact	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Affects standard of life negatively	107	26.22
Obstruction in various ongoing family developmental plans	30	7.30
Decreases social and economic status	148	36.30
Polarization of classes	39	9.60
Affects education and marriage of children	84	20.58
Total	408	100

*Multiple response question, N=408

Table 1.6: Impact of problems faced in marketing of produce

10. CONCLUSION

Agriculture is being replaced by horticulture because of greater need and demand of horticultural produce in concerned markets. It is concluded by the study that most of farmers are selling their product to pre-harvest contractor/artiya because of their unsound economic status, whereas lesser number sell it directly to commission agents in markets. The study also shows much difference between preferred and actual marketing of the product. The direct marketing is preferred over pre-harvest/artiya based marketing. It is because direct marketing saves at least the commission of pre-harvest contractor and improves their social and economic status besides keeps them free to bargain on rates from commission agents in markets and enables them to withhold their produce during low market rates. In contrast, the reasons for pre-harvest marketing are to avail money any time during the need arises and low economic background of farmers due to which they fail to wait till the harvest of their product.

The marketing of the product is very unsound in the region as of various problems which are being faced by the farmers. The most of the farmers face marketing problems in processing and distribution of their produce. The various marketing problems faced by the farmers rang from lack of markets and cold stores to unawareness about proper marketing and lack of direct contact with exporters besides high transportation and commission rates. The impact of marketing problems is multidimensional and ranges from decrease in social and economic status of cultivators to negative affect on standard of life and effect on education and marriage of children to polarization of classes besides leads to obstruction in various ongoing family developmental plans and programs. It is obvious from the conclusions drawn that marketing of the produce greatly affects the social and economic status of the farmers. The sound marketing enhances the standard of life while as its unsoundness negatively affects their developmental various aspects.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I am highly thankful to my supervisor Dr. Manmohan Singh Gill and Dr. Rachana Sharma for their kind guidance.

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